

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN TYPES OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES

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ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ВИДОВ КРИПТОВАЛЮТ

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Abstract

The nature of cryptocurrency consists of a technical and financial component. It has a complex multi-level classification system based on a variety of mechanisms with different functions. Certain characteristic features make it possible to classify cryptocurrencies depending on the purpose of creation, degree of activity, type, type of regulation, innovation, recognition by the state, type of creator. The distribution of cryptocurrencies into classes/subspecies/categories allows them to be classified depending on the mining method; generation system; encryption algorithm; emission parameter; price dynamics; purpose and type of creation. Understanding the essence of the classification of cryptocurrencies will allow them to be integrated into the financial system and legislative norms for the development of the digital asset market.

Аннотация

Природа криптовалюты состоит из технической и финансовой составляющей. Она обладает сложной многоуровневой системой классификации, основанной на множестве механизмов с разными функциями. Определенные характерные признаки позволяют классифицировать криптовалюту в зависимости от цели создания, степени активности, вида, типа регулирования, инноваций, признания государством, типа создателя. Распределение криптовалют на классы/подвиды/разряды позволяет классифицировать их в зависимости от метода добычи; системы генерации; алгоритма шифрования; параметра эмиссии; динамики котировок; назначения и типа создания. Понимание сути классификация криптовалют позволит интегрировать их в финансовую систему и законодательные нормы для развития рынка цифровых активов.

Keywords: digital assets, tokenization, distributed registries, smart contracts, stocks, blockchain, cryptocurrency, USDT, BUSD, USDC, mining

Ключевые слова: цифровые активы, токенизация, распределенные реестры, смарт-контракты, акции, блокчейн, криптовалюта, USDT, BUSD, USDC, майнинг

The relevance of this work is due to the high importance of studying the problems of pricing in the cryptocurrency market, which have received their rapid development against the background of a combination of fairly soft monetary policy of key central banks during the coronavirus pandemic, active search for profitability by investors under sanctions restrictions, as well as the needs of individuals and legal entities in instant payments. After all, the purpose of creating cryptocurrencies, as a decentralized type of digital currency, using cryptography as security and control over the creation of new units, is to provide a convenient means of payment, potentially attractive from an investment position. As well as giving cryptocurrencies an anonymous character, allowing them to circumvent regulatory restrictions by eliminating intermediaries, which include banks and payment systems, and transferring the verification function of transactions to a distributed ledger system.

The classification criteria of cryptocurrencies are quite variable, but first you need to determine the classification levels that K.O. Korchagina suggests for consideration [1]:

- The 1st level of classification of types of cryptocurrencies is represented by a division into types depending on certain characteristic features;
- The 2nd level of classification of types of cryptocurrencies is represented by grouping or distributing cryptocurrencies of one type into classes, subspecies or categories.

Let's consider the classification of types of cryptocurrencies depending on certain characteristic features.

1. A.S. Abramov suggests distinguishing cryptocurrencies depending on the purpose of creation, highlighting [2]:

- targeted cryptocurrencies characterized by an implementation process related to the focus on the final result (the purpose of creation may be fraud, pursuit of

financial interest (investment cryptocurrencies), experimental goals (testing new technologies), etc.);

- non-targeted cryptocurrencies characterized by the creation process occurring as a result of a technical failure (an example is the creation of forks (clones) - offshoots from the original digital currencies with certain changes in functions).

2. N.V. Anokhin and A.I. Shmyreva classify cryptocurrencies depending on the degree of activity, highlighting [3]:

- active cryptocurrencies that have not reached the upper limit of the issue, acting as potentially promising types for investment (there is a demand for cryptocurrency);

- inactive cryptocurrencies characterized by reaching the upper limit of issuance, lack of support from developers or the community, which do not cause investment attractiveness on the exchange (there is no demand for cryptocurrency).

3. M.S. Bondarev classifies cryptocurrencies depending on the type, calling [4]:

- original cryptocurrencies, the creation process of which at the time of development is characterized by the use of original source code other than previously implemented cryptocurrencies;

- forks (clones), which are a type of cryptocurrency, the creation process of which is due to a technical failure or the use of existing source code of another cryptocurrency.

4. A.V. Voloshin and A.E. Guseynikova distinguish cryptocurrencies depending on the type of regulation, the central administrator, offering for consideration [5]:

- a centralized system characterized by the administrator's right to regulate and make changes to the issuance process in order to control cryptocurrencies (examples include cryptocurrencies USDT, BUSD, USDC);

- a decentralized system (distributed system) characterized by the absence of a central regulatory body or other body with a management mechanism (examples include cryptocurrencies Bitcoin and Ethereum).

5. E.N. Gavrilova and A.S. Demjanjuk supplement the classification with an innovation-dependent criterion [6]:

- innovative cryptocurrencies, the creation of which is based on previously unrealized technologies;

- non-innovative cryptocurrencies, the creation of which is based on the use of previously implemented technologies.

6. D.A. Durdyeva and A.A. Trapizonyan expanded the approach to classification by the criterion of recognition by the state, the presence of current legislation defining the status of a particular cryptocurrency, highlighting [7]:

- a regulated cryptocurrency, the status of which is determined and fixed by the regulatory legal acts of a particular state;

- an unregulated cryptocurrency, the status of which is not determined and is not fixed by the regulatory legal acts of a particular state.

7. I.A. Emelin divides the cryptocurrency depending on the type of creator who provided the development and implementation, highlighting [8]:

- an author's cryptocurrency that was created by a specific individual, organization, or government;

- an anonymous cryptocurrency, the authorship of which was not confirmed at the time of creation;

- a cryptocurrency that was created as a result of a technical failure, in other words, in the process of diverging the block chain.

The second direction of classification should be called the types of cryptocurrencies.

1. F.P. Kichedzhi and M.Z. Tsiperson distinguish cryptocurrencies depending on the mining method [9]:

1.1. Cryptocurrency can be mined through the use of a technical method (mining). The method consists in using the computing power of technology to maintain a distributed platform, as well as create new blocks for a fee. Mining can only be carried out in networks with the Proof-of-Work (PoW) algorithm. A large number of miners, acting independently of each other, take part in the creation of each new block. An alternative algorithm can be called Proof-of-Stake (PoS). It is characterized by the creation of a new block by one validator, which is randomly selected among all validators of the network, but taking into account the available amount of cryptocurrency. In this case, cryptocurrency mining is carried out by stacking. The following types of cryptocurrencies can be mentioned as examples: Bitcoin, Dogecoin, Monero.

Depending on the number of participants, you can select:

- independent mining, when the number of participants does not exceed one, its own equipment is used, and the profit goes to one miner;

- joint mining (mining with the help of pools – a common fund), when the number of participants is more than one, technical computing abilities are accumulated in a single system, and profits are distributed among all participants according to the contribution to the computing power of the pool;

- cloud mining, when the mining process is carried out by a third-party organization that provides its own computing power for leasing, but performs operations on behalf of the client.

Depending on the equipment used for mining, there are:

- mining carried out using GPU (graphics processing unit) - graphics processors;

- extraction carried out using the CPU (central processing unit) - the central processor;

- mining carried out using ASIC (application-specific integrated circuit) - specialized integrated circuits;

- extraction carried out using FPGA (field-programmable gate array).

1.2. Cryptocurrency is mined using the financial method through the use of classical financial instruments and purchase and sale transactions. Ethereum, Solana, Toncoin can serve as an example. The following methods are distinguished:

- an investment method that allows you to purchase cryptocurrency on exchanges using fiat money;
- a currency method that allows you to exchange cryptocurrency for other types of cryptocurrencies.

2. A.V. Konovalov suggests classifying cryptocurrencies depending on the generation system, methods of protecting distributed systems from entering false information (creating fake transactions and blocks) [10]:

- POW is a generation system, the principle of which is the need for the requesting party to perform some computational actions that protect the distributed system from external attacks;
- POS is a generation system based on the principle of having a larger unit of account of the total number of cryptocurrencies;
- a hybrid system involving the use of several generation systems (mainly POW and POS) at the same time, as well as alternately;
- the use of other systems, examples of which may be Proof-of-Burn, Proof-of-Capacity, etc.

3. K.O. Korchagina considers it important to classify depending on the implemented encryption algorithm - methods of converting an array of data in the blockchain system, which may differ in mathematical properties and algorithmic features (examples are: bit depth, computational complexity, etc.). The choice of a specific hashing algorithm is determined by the specifics of the tasks set, which allows you to distinguish [11]:

- cryptocurrencies using the same type of encryption system implementing the same encryption algorithm (for example, SHA-2 or Scrypt);
- cryptocurrencies that use a mixed encryption system that implements two or more encryption algorithms at the same time.

4. M.E. Kosov suggests classifying cryptocurrencies depending on the emission parameter, distinguishing [12]:

4.1. Cryptocurrencies by volume of issue:

- with a limited issue, having a certain upper limit on the issue, limited by technological solutions (an example is Bitcoin);
- without limitation of emissions that do not have an upper limit of output by implemented technological solutions.

4.2. Cryptocurrencies by type of issue, depending

on the speed of coin generation, highlighting:

- ordinary issue, the issue of which is determined by the efforts of the community generating the cryptocurrency, and does not depend on the administrative resource;
 - accelerated (one-time) issue, when the type of issue that is used, for example, for ICO, is characterized by the generation of coins by a regulatory administrative resource.
5. M.A. Chistyakov classifies types of cryptocurrencies depending on the dynamics of quotations, highlighting [13]:
- stablecoins, which are cryptocurrencies whose value is linked to a specific fiat currency (dollar, euro, etc.) or a physical asset (gold, silver, etc.); an example would be the USDT stablecoin, linked to the US dollar;
 - traditional cryptocurrencies, the value of which is not tied to anything, is determined by the characteristics of the project, volatility is not limited (an example is Bitcoin);
 - new crypto projects – new tokens that have high volatility, can show rapid growth and decline in short time intervals (an example is the AxieInfinity game coin (AXS)).

6. K.D. Shilov additionally spills types of cryptocurrencies depending on the purpose [14]:

- replacing traditional currency in the digital world (for example, stablecoins that are linked to real money);
- payment and reward system (for example, project tokens that are created as currency in online games);
- calculations in the crypto world, representing the widest group of cryptocurrencies;
- others, among which you can distinguish meme currencies that have or do not have their own blockchain (for example, Dogecoin).

All the types of cryptocurrencies discussed above are the basis of the most popular classification, which was described in their work by M.R. Safiullin, L.A. Yelshin and A.A. Abdukaeva [15]. According to the authors' approach, cryptocurrencies are divided into three categories: tokens, coins and coins of networks (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Types of Cryptocurrencies

Source: developed by the author

Cohens work on the basis of their own blockchain, the main purpose is the ability to be a means of payment and serve as a substitute for the traditional financial system (examples may be Bitcoin (BTC), Litecoin (LTC), Monero (XMR), etc.).

Tokens are cryptocurrencies that operate on the basis of another blockchain, since they do not have their own. They are the largest group in terms of the number

of crypto assets, as they require less effort to create. They work on the Ethereum and BNB SmartChain networks; act as the right to own something. They distinguish:

- stablecoins (centralized (USDT, USDC, BUSD, TEUR), decentralized (DAI, MIM, LUSD), algorithmic (FEI, FRAX, UST), commodity (PAXG, XAUT));

- tokens of exchanges (centralized exchanges (BNB, LEO, OKB); decentralized exchanges (UNI, CAKE, CRV));
- application tokens are coins of gaming platforms, meta universes and other projects (AXS, SAND, GMT);
- tokens – do not have their own blockchain, they can be supported by different networks and blockchains.

Network coins powered by smart contracts are a small group of cryptocurrencies in which platform networks create coins to perform the function of internal payments. Examples of this group of crypto assets: represented by: ETH - coin of the Ethereum network; SOL - coin of the Solana network; BNB - coin of the BNB Smart Chain network; TRX - coin of the Tron network; DOT - coin of the Polkadot network, etc. [16]

In general, the classification of types of cryptocurrencies is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Types of cryptocurrencies

Classification criteria	Types of cryptocurrencies
1. Depending on the purpose of creation	Targeted and Non-targeted cryptocurrencies
2. Depending on the degree of activity	Active and Inactive Cryptocurrencies
3. Depending on the type	Original cryptocurrencies and forks (clones)
4. Depending on the type of regulation	Centralized and Decentralized Cryptocurrencies
5. Depending on the innovation	Innovative and non-innovative cryptocurrencies
6. Depending on the recognition by the State	Regulated and Unregulated Cryptocurrencies
7. Depending on the type of creator who provided the development and implementation	An author's, anonymous, cryptocurrency created as a result of a technical failure
8. Depending on the extraction method	Through the use of mining (independent, collaborative, cloud), using the financial method (investment, currency)
9. Depending on the generation system, methods of protection of distributed systems	POW - generation system; POS - generation system; hybrid system; other
10. Depending on the implemented encryption algorithm	Cryptocurrencies using the same type and mixed encryption systems
11. Depending on the emission parameter	Cryptocurrencies by volume of issue (with and without limitation); by type of issue depending on the speed of coin generation (regular, accelerated)
12. Depending on the dynamics of quotations	Stablecoins, traditional and new crypto projects
13. Depending on the purpose	Replacing the traditional currency in the digital world; payment and reward system; settlements in the crypto world; other
14. Depending on the type of creation	Coins, tokens, coins of networks

Source: compiled by the author

Thus, it can be concluded that the nature of cryptocurrency consists of a technical and financial component. It has a complex multi-level classification system based on a variety of mechanisms with different functions. Certain characteristic features make it possible to classify cryptocurrencies depending on the purpose of creation, degree of activity, type, type of regulation, innovation, recognition by the state, type of creator. The distribution of cryptocurrencies into classes/subspecies/categories allows them to be classified depending on the mining method; generation system; encryption algorithm; the issue parameter; the dynamics of quotations; the purpose and type of creation. For integration into the financial system of the Russian Federation, there are prerequisites - classification parameters that meet the requirements of implementation in the Russian Federation - the presence of a goal, activity status, regulated by legislation with a centralized management system, if there is an officially registered author or developer. This tool is innovative, so its implementation will be accompanied by the development of the financial and technological industries, and the synergy of these areas will create prerequisites for the large-scale development of other industries.

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